

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

Protocol for Soil Sampling

**Version 1
May/2020**

1. Sampling time points

Soil samples from four different fields will be taken in seven different time points (S1-S7) within the 1-year sampling period, in each European region. Meadow (Ms1-4) and forest soil (Fs1-4) samples will be collected as well serving as controls for the soil, 4 times each within the 1-year sampling period, matching their sampling times with soil sampling times S1, S4, S5 and S7 (see sample references above). The sampling time points are:

- S1- Baseline before fertilization
- S2- One day after fertilization (manure / artificial fertilizer)
- S3- One week after fertilization
- S4- Six weeks after fertilization
- S5- Eighteen weeks after fertilization
- S6- Just before harvest
- S7- After harvest

2. Description of the catchment areas in the different countries

Austria

The Hydrology Open Air Laboratory (HOAL) catchment area is situated in Petzenkirchen, Lower Austria, 100 km from Vienna. The catchment area is 66 ha and is divided in: 87% arable land, 5% pasture, 6% forested, 2% paved area. The dominant soil types are: Cambisols and Planosols (also Gleysols - close to the stream). The farmers use natural fertilizers - swine manure - and the crops are mainly winter - wheat and maize. The natural surface water outlet of the catchment is a stream, which tends to be feed by a mixture of tile drainage water, diffuse inflow from the shallow aquifer, spring water and surface water from the wetland. The catchment is monitored in different locations, regarding several compartments and variables in order to improve understanding of different natural processes such as dynamics of the nutrients (P, Na), sediment monitoring/deposition and resuspension in the stream, groundwater level/characteristics and surface water characteristics.

In Austria, the soil from four fields, three with corn (C1, C2, C3) and one with wheat (C4) will be sampled in seven different time points (S1-S7). In fields C1 and C3 pig manure (M) will be applied, while in fields C2 and C4 an artificial fertilizer (AF) will be used.

- C1, Corn with Manure (*Graf 9*)
- C2, Corn with Artificial Fertilizer (*BVW4*)
- C3, Corn with Manure (*Huber 39*)
- C4, Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer (*Jäger 16*)

Figure 1. Overview of the Austrian fields (C1-C4) where samples are collected.

Portugal

The Hydrology Open Air Laboratory (HOAL) catchment area is situated in Santarém, Vale de Santarém, 75 km from Lisbon.

The catchment area is 230 ha and is divided in: 17.6% arable land, 38.2% pasture, 13.2% forested, 30.9% paved area.

The dominant soil types are: Loamic Calcari Cambisol (CMcalo) and Gleyic Fluvisol (FLgl). Both soils with a sandy loam texture, increasing the clay and silt content to a depth of more than one meter, with an average porosity of 50%, average levels of organic matter (M.O) and a slightly alkaline pH.

The farmers use natural fertilizers - pig manure - and the crops are mainly oats, but also wheat

and maize during Autumn (September and October). The fertilization is carried out by soil spreading of the effluents prior to cultures installation.

In Portugal, the soil from four fields, two with corn (C1, C2) and two with wheat (C3, C4) will be sampled in seven different time points (S1-7), within the 1-year sampling period, starting Autumn 2020. In fields C1 and C3 pig manure (M) will be applied, while in fields C2 and C4, an artificial fertilizer (AF) will be used.

- C1, Corn with Manure
- C2, Corn with Artificial Fertilizer
- C3, Wheat with Manure
- C4, Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer

Czech Republic

Czech test fields are situated in Karlovy Vary region, 150 km from Prague. The dominant soil types are cambisols. The farm company manages about 1500 ha of agricultural land which is divided in: 40 % of arable land and 60 % of pasture. The farmers use natural fertilizers – swine and cow manure - and the crops are mainly winter – wheat and oilseed rape. In the area, there are several streams and ponds catching the surface water.

In Czech Republic, the soil from four fields will be sampled in seven different time points (S1-7), within the 1-year sampling period, starting spring 2020. In fields C1 and C3 pig manure (M) will be applied, while in fields C2 and C4, an artificial fertilizer (AF) will be used:

- C1, Wheat with Manure
- C2, Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer
- C3, Wheat with Manure
- C4, Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer

Estonia

Estonia will test fields associated with a farm located about 30 kilometres from Tartu. The main crop is potatoes but for the project purposes wheat will be grown on small test fields. The area contains 50% agricultural land and 50% forest. Small waterbodies (rivers, ponds) are associated with the fields.

In Estonia, the soil from four fields with wheat will be sampled in seven different time points (S1-7), within the 1-year sampling period, starting May 2020. In fields C1 and C3 pig manure (M) will be applied, while in fields C2 and C4, an artificial fertilizer (AF) will be used:

- C1, Wheat with Manure
- C2, Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer
- C3, Wheat with Manure
- C4, Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer

3. Equipment

- PET sterile soil bags
- Plastic containers

- PET dark bottles
- Driller (*Purckhauer*) and hummer
- Marker (water resistant)
- Rubber gloves
- Disinfectant (sodiumhypochlorite-Danklorix-10%)
- Sterile distilled water
- Storage box (with cooling ice packs)
- Garbage bags(waste)

4. Sampling procedure

- Acidify in the laboratory each of the tubes intended for element analysis with two drops of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃, for trace metal analysis grade).
- Collect meteorological conditions and information on the soil characteristics (moisture, pH, %clay, %sand, %humus, etc). The moisture status of the soil at the time of sampling should allow ploughing; if the soil is too dry or wet, the results of some parameters are not meaningful.
- Select four fields (C1-C4) and two controls [meadow (Ms1-4) and forest (Fs1-4)]. For increasing comparability only soils of the same soil type (chernozem or cambisol or fluvisol as the main soil types in e.g. Austrian agricultural fields) should be collected and compared by the project partners.
- Define the sampling area (zones/grids) by identifying and marking ten extraction points (X systematic pattern). This guarantees a representative area.
- Take a picture of each extraction point and capture the GPS coordinates.
- Put on the rubber gloves to prevent contamination.
- Place the driller over the extraction point to be sampled and insert it into the ground with the hummer up to 15 cm depth.
- Pull the driller up and introduce the soil in the sterile bag (70-100 g). Note that it may be necessary to fill the driller two or more times in order to have the desired quantity.
- Homogenize by hand the sample without touching the inner part of the sterile bag.
- Repeat the same process (steps 3-7) until having ten soil samples of 70-100 g each.
- Combine the ten subsamples into a single composite sample of approximately 750 g in a sterile PET bag. To do so the 10 subsamples must be thoroughly mixed and no air should remain inside.
- Seal the bag tightly and label it with its corresponding code (see section 4) with a water resistant marker.

- Clean the driller between fields with a solution containing sodium hypochlorite and rinse it with distilled water, so that no soil remains on the driller.
- Change the gloves to prevent cross-contamination and repeat the same steps in other field (steps 2-10).
- Let all samples dry out for 42 hours at room temperature.
- Sterilize the stainless steel sieves with 80% ethanol and then rinse them with distilled water (**do not use sodium hypochlorite!**). Between each sample this cleaning process should be done.
- Sieve (mesh size: 2mm) each sample avoiding cross-contamination with the material.
- Distribute samples in the different containers according to the aimed analysis and keep them until transport under the conditions displayed in **Table 1**.
- Transport samples immediately to the laboratory under refrigeration (4-8°C) or with ice-packs, depending on the subsequent analysis (Table 1).
Do not freeze samples intended for bacteriology/molecular analysis!

Table 1. Distribution and transport conditions for soil samples.

Analysis	Task	Amount	Container	Transport /Conservation until processing
Antibiotics (WP4)	4.5	25 g	PET dark bottles	-20 °C
Elements (WP4)	4.7	300-400 g	PET sterile bags	4 °C
Herbicides (WP4)	4.6	100 g	Plastic containers	4 °C
Bacteriology (WP2 and WP3)	2.3, 2.4, 3.1	50-100 g	Sterile bags	4 °C

- Process samples according to the different aims (**figure 2**) and within a maximum of 24h. This is particularly important when microbiological and molecular analysis are foreseen.
- Store remains of unprocessed samples at -20°C.

Figure 2. Workflow representing the amount of soil needed for each type of analysis within the FED-AMR project.

5. Sample identifiers for soil samples

The following sample identifiers will be used along the duration of the project.

Table 2. Distribution and transport conditions established for soil samples.

Sample Reference	Description	Type of crop	Scheduled date
Austria			
AT20-S1-C1	Austria, Baseline soil, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Mar 20
AT20-S2-C1	Austria, soil +1d, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Apr 20
AT20-S3-C1	Austria, soil 1w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Apr 20
AT20-S4-C1	Austria, soil 6w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	May 20
AT20-S5-C1	Austria, soil 18w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Aug 20
AT20-S6-C1	Austria, soil just before harvest, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Sep 20
AT20-S7-C1	Austria, soil after harvest, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Oct 20
AT20-S1-C2	Austria, Baseline soil, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Mar 20
AT20-S2-C2	Austria, soil +1d, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
AT20-S3-C2	Austria, soil 1w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
AT20-S4-C2	Austria, soil 6w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
AT20-S5-C2	Austria, soil 18w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
AT20-S6-C2	Austria, soil just before harvest, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Sep 20
AT20-S7-C2	Austria, soil after harvest, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
AT20-S1-C3	Austria, Baseline soil, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Mar 20
AT20-S2-C3	Austria, soil +1d, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Apr 20
AT20-S3-C3	Austria, soil 1w, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Apr 20
AT20-S4-C3	Austria, soil 6w, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	May 20
AT20-S5-C3	Austria, soil 18w, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Aug 20
AT20-S6-C3	Austria, soil just before harvest, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Sep 20
AT20-S7-C3	Austria, soil after harvest, crop 3	Corn (2) with Manure	Oct 20
AT20-S1-C4	Austria, Baseline soil, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Mar 20
AT20-S2-C4	Austria, soil +1d, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
AT20-S3-C4	Austria, soil 1w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
AT20-S4-C4	Austria, soil 6w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
AT20-S5-C4	Austria, soil 18w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Jul 20 – not possible
AT20-S6-C4	Austria, soil just before harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Jul 20
AT20-S7-C4	Austria, soil after harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
AT20-Fs1	Austria, baseline soil, forest	Control	Mar 20
AT20-Fs2	Austria, soil S4, forest	Control	May 20
AT20-Fs3	Austria, soil S5, forest	Control	Aug 20

AT20-Fs4	Austria, soil S7, forest	Control	Oct 20
AT20-Ms1	Austria, meadow, baseline	Control	Mar 20
AT20-Ms2	Austria, soil S4, meadow	Control	May 20
AT20-Ms3	Austria, soil S5, meadow	Control	Aug 20
AT20-Ms4	Austria, soil S7, meadow	Control	Oct 20
Portugal			
PT20-S1-C1	Portugal, Baseline soil, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S2-C1	Portugal, soil +1d, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S3-C1	Portugal, soil 1w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S4-C1	Portugal, soil 6w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Nov 20
PT21-S5-C1	Portugal, soil 18w, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Feb 21
PT21-S6-C1	Portugal, soil just before harvest, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Apr 21
PT21-S7-C1	Portugal, soil after harvest, crop 1	Corn with Manure	Apr 21
PT20-S1-C2	Portugal, Baseline soil, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S2-C2	Portugal, soil +1d, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S3-C2	Portugal, soil 1w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S4-C2	Portugal, soil 6w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Nov 20
PT21-S5-C2	Portugal, soil 18w, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Feb 21
PT21-S6-C2	Portugal, soil just before harvest, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21
PT21-S7-C2	Portugal, soil after harvest, crop 2	Corn with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21
PT20-S1-C3	Portugal, Baseline soil, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S2-C3	Portugal, soil +1d, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S3-C3	Portugal, soil 1w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Oct 20
PT20-S4-C3	Portugal, soil 6w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Nov 20
PT21-S5-C3	Portugal, soil 18w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Feb 21
PT21-S6-C3	Portugal, soil just before harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 21
PT21-S7-C3	Portugal, soil after harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 21
PT20-S1-C4	Portugal, Baseline soil, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S2-C4	Portugal, soil +1d, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S3-C4	Portugal, soil 1w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
PT20-S4-C4	Portugal, soil 6w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Nov 20
PT21-S5-C4	Portugal, soil 18w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Feb 21
PT21-S6-C4	Portugal, soil just before harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21
PT21-S7-C4	Portugal, soil after harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 21
PT20-Fs1	Portugal, baseline soil, forest	Control	Oct 20
PT20-Fs2	Portugal, soil S4, forest	Control	Nov 20
PT21-Fs3	Portugal, soil S5, forest	Control	Feb 21
PT21-Fs4	Portugal, soil S7, forest	Control	Apr 21
PT20-Ms1	Portugal, meadow, baseline	Control	Oct 20
PT20-Ms2	Portugal, soil S4, meadow	Control	Nov 20

PT21-Ms3	Portugal, soil S5, meadow	Control	Feb 21
PT21-Ms4	Portugal, soil S7, meadow	Control	Apr 21
Czech Republic			
CZ20-S1-C1	Czech Republic, Baseline soil, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S2-C1	Czech Republic, soil +1d, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S3-C1	Czech Republic, soil 1w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S4-C1	Czech Republic, soil 6w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Jun 20
CZ20-S5-C1	Czech Republic, soil 18w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S6-C1	Czech Republic, soil just before harvest, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S7-C1	Czech Republic, soil after harvest, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S1-C2	Czech Republic, Baseline soil, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S2-C2	Czech Republic, soil +1d, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S3-C2	Czech Republic, soil 1w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S4-C2	Czech Republic, soil 6w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Jun 20
CZ20-S5-C2	Czech Republic, soil 18w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-S6-C2	Czech Republic, soil just before harvest, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-S7-C2	Czech Republic, soil after harvest, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-S1-C3	Czech Republic, Baseline soil, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S2-C3	Czech Republic, soil +1d, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S3-C3	Czech Republic, soil 1w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Apr 20
CZ20-S4-C3	Czech Republic, soil 6w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Jun 20
CZ20-S5-C3	Czech Republic, soil 18w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S6-C3	Czech Republic, soil just before harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S7-C3	Czech Republic, soil after harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Aug 20
CZ20-S1-C4	Czech Republic, Baseline soil, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S2-C4	Czech Republic, soil +1d, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S3-C4	Czech Republic, soil 1w, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Apr 20
CZ20-S4-C4	Czech Republic, soil 6w, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Jun 20
CZ20-S5-C4	Czech Republic, soil 18w, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-S6-C4	Czech Republic, soil just before harvest, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20
CZ20-S7-C4	Czech Republic, soil after harvest, crop 4	Oilseed rape with Artificial Fertilizer	Aug 20

CZ20-Fs1	Czech Republic, baseline soil, forest	Control	Apr 20
CZ20-Fs2	Czech Republic, soil S4, forest	Control	Jun 20
CZ20-Fs3	Czech Republic, soil S5, forest	Control	Aug 20
CZ20-Fs4	Czech Republic, soil S7, forest	Control	Aug 20
CZ20-Ms1	Czech Republic, meadow, baseline	Control	Apr 20
CZ20-Ms2	Czech Republic, soil S4, meadow	Control	Jun 20
CZ20-Ms3	Czech Republic, soil S5, meadow	Control	Aug 20
CZ20-Ms4	Czech Republic, soil S7, meadow	Control	Aug 20
Estonia			
EE20-S1-C1	Estonia, Baseline soil, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S2-C1	Estonia, soil +1d, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S3-C1	Estonia, soil 1w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S4-C1	Estonia, soil 6w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	June 20
EE21-S5-C1	Estonia, soil 18w, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Sept 20
EE21-S6-C1	Estonia, soil just before harvest, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Sept 20
EE21-S7-C1	Estonia, soil after harvest, crop 1	Wheat with Manure	Oct 20
EE20-S1-C2	Estonia, Baseline soil, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S2-C2	Estonia, soil +1d, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S3-C2	Estonia, soil 1w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S4-C2	Estonia, soil 6w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	June 20
EE21-S5-C2	Estonia, soil 18w, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Sept 20
EE21-S6-C2	Estonia, soil just before harvest, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Sept 20
EE21-S7-C2	Estonia, soil after harvest, crop 2	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
EE20-S1-C3	Estonia, Baseline soil, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S2-C3	Estonia, soil +1d, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S3-C3	Estonia, soil 1w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	May 20
EE20-S4-C3	Estonia, soil 6w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	June 20
EE21-S5-C3	Estonia, soil 18w, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Sept 20
EE21-S6-C3	Estonia, soil just before harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Sept 20
EE21-S7-C3	Estonia, soil after harvest, crop 3	Wheat with Manure	Oct 20
EE20-S1-C4	Estonia, Baseline soil, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S2-C4	Estonia, soil +1d, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S3-C4	Estonia, soil 1w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	May 20
EE20-S4-C4	Estonia, soil 6w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	June 20
EE21-S5-C4	Estonia, soil 18w, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Sept 20
EE21-S6-C4	Estonia, soil just before harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Sept 20

EE21-S7-C4	Estonia, soil after harvest, crop 4	Wheat with Artificial Fertilizer	Oct 20
EE20-Fs1	Estonia, baseline soil, forest	Control	May 20
EE20-Fs2	Estonia, soil S4, forest	Control	Jun 20
EE21-Fs3	Estonia, soil S5, forest	Control	Aug 20
EE21-Fs4	Estonia, soil S7, forest	Control	Oct 20
EE20-Ms1	Estonia, meadow, baseline	Control	May 20
EE20-Ms2	Estonia, soil S4, meadow	Control	Jun 20
EE21-Ms3	Estonia, soil S5, meadow	Control	Aug 20
EE21-Ms4	Estonia, soil S7, meadow	Control	Oct 20

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